

Synthesis, Structural Studies and Antimicrobial Activities of some Metal Complexes derived from 7-(α -Phenyl- α -*o/m*-chloroanilinomethyl)-8-quinolinol

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Solid complexes of 7-(α -phenyl- α -*o/m*-chloroanilinomethyl)-8-quinolinol (POCAMQ/PMCAMQ) with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO₂^{II} have been prepared and characterised. They have also been tested for their antimicrobial activities.

A simple but interesting Mannich type of reaction is known to occur with aromatic amine, benzaldehyde and 8-quinolinol giving the biologically active 7-substituted-8-quinolinol derivatives. Several workers extended this reaction to different aromatic and heterocyclic amines and aldehyde to obtain potential drugs¹ and analytical reagents². Mannich bases assumed new importance because of their antibacterial and antifungal activities³. Stereochemical features of some new Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} complexes of Mannich bases have been studied⁴. The present communication reports studies on 7-(α -phenyl- α -*o*-chloroanilinomethyl)-8-quinolinol (POCAMQ), 7-(α -phenyl- α -*m*-chloroanilinomethyl)-8-quinolinol (PMCAMQ) and their metal complexes with various metal ions. The structure of the complexes has been established using analytical, thermal, magnetic, ir and electronic spectral data.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic, analytical and electrical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1. Elemental analyses of the complexes indicate 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry.

Magnetic and reflectance spectral studies : Cu^{II} complexes of POCAMQ and PMCAMQ show magnetic moment of 1.75 and 1.79 B.M. respectively, which indicates square-planar geometry. The reflectance spectra show two bands. The one at 14 150-14 725 and 25 320-25 412 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} transition, which is in the range generally observed for planar Cu^{II} complexes. The other band at 25 320-25 412 cm⁻¹ is due to ligand-metal charge transfer transition⁵. The Ni^{II} complexes show magnetic moment in the range 2.93-3.20 B.M. which is close to that required (2.8-3.3) for octahedral stereo chemistry. The reflectance spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 9 195-9 290, 15 495-15 564 and 25 510-25 560 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F), ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively, considering an octahedral geometry. The structure is also further confirmed by the ratio ν_2/ν_1 (1.66-1.69), the value expected for octahedral structure⁶. The Co^{II} complexes have a magnetic moment in the range 3.92-3.95 B.M. which is the expected range (3.9-4.44 B.M.) for a tetrahedral geometry⁷. The reflectance spectra of the Co^{II} complexes

exhibit three bands at 8 885-8 970, 15 380-15 495 and 24 515-25 625 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁(F), ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁(P) and charge transfer transitions respectively, considering a tetrahedral geometry⁷. The magnetic moment observed in the range 5.45-5.48 B.M. for the Mn^{II} complexes is lower than the spin-only value (5.92 B.M.), which may be due to aerial oxidation of Mn^{II} to Mn^{III} during synthesis. The reflectance spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes exhibit three absorption bands at 13 715-13 875, 15 432-15 690 and 22 727-24 415 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(⁴G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(⁴G) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴E_g, ⁴A_{1g}(⁴G) transitions respectively, considering an octahedral symmetry⁸. The spectra of the UO₂^{II} chelates exhibit bands at 19 710-20 000 and 25 670-26 315 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ¹Σ_g⁺ → ³π_u and charge transfer transitions respectively, for octahedral stereo-chemistry⁹. The Zn^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Hg^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are found to be diamagnetic. A tetrahedral geometry is proposed for the Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} chelates¹⁰.

Infrared spectral studies : The ir band at ~3 420 cm⁻¹ of the Mannich bases assigned to the OH bonded to N of 8-quinolinol^{11,12}, vanishes in the spectra of the metal chelates indicating the removal of H in the complex formation. A broad band around 3 320 (NH)^{12,13} and 1 580, 1 570 and 1 460 cm⁻¹ (heteroaromatic)^{12,14} have been observed in the spectra of Mannich bases and their metal chelates. A new band of medium intensity appears in the metal chelates at ~1 100-1 200 cm⁻¹ (C-O-M)¹⁵. The band at 1 600 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the Mannich bases (C=N of 8-quinolinol)^{12,16} is shifted to around 1 630 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the metal chelates indicating the involvement of nitrogen in the chelate formation¹³. New bands are observed at 640-630 (M-N) and 680-670 cm⁻¹ (M-O) in the complexes¹³. The band at 3 350-3 370 cm⁻¹ in the Mn^{II}, Ni^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes show the presence of coordinated water molecule¹⁷. Thus it may be concluded that Mannich bases act as monobasic bidentate ligand.

Electrical conductivity : The electrical conductivity (σ) of ligands and their metal chelates was studied over wide range of temperature. σ varies exponentially with the absolute temperature according to the relationship, $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp^{-E_a/kT}$, where σ is the conductivity at T K, σ_0 the specific conductivity, E_a the activation energy and k

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF CHELATES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)				σ cm ⁻¹	Activation energy eV
		M	C	H	N		
POCAMQ	White	-	73.19 (73.23)	4.68 4.72	7.73 (7.77)	8.45 × 10 ⁻¹⁴	0.169 0
Cu(POCAMQ)	Green	8.06 (8.12)	67.39 67.47	3.97 4.08	7.10 (7.16)	5.7 × 10 ⁻¹³	0.114 0
Ni(POCAMQ H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	7.13 (7.21)	64.78 64.89	3.85 3.93	6.83 (6.88)	5.69 × 10 ⁻¹⁴	0.099 6
Co(POCAMQ) ₂	Brown	7.49 (7.58)	67.81 67.87	4.10 4.11	7.12 (7.20)	4.47 × 10 ⁻¹²	0.076 3
Zn(POCAMQ) ₂	Yellow	8.29 (8.36)	64.22 67.29	3.94 4.07	7.07 (7.14)	8.5 × 10 ⁻¹³	0.058 4
Mn(POCAMQ H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	6.71 (6.78)	65.13 65.19	3.97 3.95	6.82 (6.91)	1.89 × 10 ⁻¹³	0.062 3
Hg(POCAMQ) ₂	Yellow	21.69 (21.81)	57.32 57.41	3.34 3.48	6.00 (6.09)	1.2 × 10 ⁻¹²	0.053 7
Cd(POCAMQ) ₂	Yellow	13.63 (13.51)	63.38 63.50	3.76 3.85	6.68 (6.74)	9.23 × 10 ⁻¹²	0.016 8
UO ₂ (POCAMQ H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	26.29	51.37	2.98	5.38	2.77 × 10 ⁻¹²	0.049 4
PMCAMQ	White	-	73.16 (73.23)	4.68 4.72	7.72 (7.77)	2.62 × 10 ⁻¹²	0.162 0
Cu(PMCAMQ) ₂	Green	8.10 (8.12)	67.34 67.47	4.0 4.08	7.12 (7.16)	7.1 × 10 ⁻¹³	0.076 8
Ni(PMCAMQ H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	7.16 (7.22)	64.87 64.89	3.89 3.93	6.86 (6.88)	1.2 × 10 ⁻¹¹	0.056 9
Co(PMCAMQ) ₂	Brown	7.49 (7.58)	67.76 67.87	4.08 4.11	7.13 (7.20)	1.0 × 10 ⁻¹²	0.048 3
Zn(PMCAMQ) ₂	Yellow	8.24 (8.36)	67.21 67.29	4.0 4.08	7.11 (7.14)	2.0 × 10 ⁻¹⁴	0.071 9
Mn(PMCAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	Brown	6.71 (6.78)	65.13 65.19	3.86 3.95	6.83 (6.91)	3.82 × 10 ⁻¹²	0.046 0
Hg(PMCAMQ) ₂	Yellow	21.72 (21.81)	57.28 57.42	3.37 3.48	6.0 (6.09)	2.64 × 10 ⁻¹⁴	0.054 0
Cd(PMCAMQ) ₂	Yellow	13.47 (13.51)	63.36 63.50	3.81 3.85	6.68 (6.74)	3.2 × 10 ⁻¹³	0.068 1
UO ₂ (PMCAMQ H ₂ O) ₂	Red	26.25 (26.34)	51.48 51.51	3.02 3.12	5.29 (5.46)	1.83 × 10 ⁻¹³	0.052 8

* (POCAMQ) = anion of POCAMQ; (PMCAMQ) = anion of PMCAMQ.

the Boltzman constant. The activation energy decreases in the order : POCAMQ > Cu > Ni > Co > Mn > Zn > Hg > UO₂ > Cd and PMCAMQ > Cu > Zn > Cd > Ni > Hg > UO₂ > Co > Mn, which is in partial agreement with the reported results¹⁸

Thermal study : TG and DSC data (Table 2) reveal that metal chelates follow single step decomposition. From TG traces, it is observed that the rate of decomposition of metal chelates is faster than that of the parent ligand. The Broido method was applied to TG data to determine the energy of

activation and the order of reaction¹⁹. The loss of two water molecules in the Mn^{II}, Ni^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes at 160° indicates that these molecules are coordinated to the respective metal ions²⁰. The trend in thermal stability of the metal chelates on the basis of E_a values is decreasing order is POCAMQ > UO₂ > Mn > Zn > Hg > Cu > Ni > Co > Cd, and PMCAMQ > UO₂^{II} > Cu > Zn > Co > Mn > Ni > Hg > Cd. DSC traces show a single endothermic peak in the Mannich bases, which is due to melting transition. The metal complexes show single exothermic peak in all traces

TABLE 2—TG AND DSC DATA OF THE LIGAND AND CHELATES

Compd.	TG					DSC			
	T_S °C	T_E °C	Weight-loss %	E_a kcal mol ⁻¹	n	T_S °C	T_E °C	Peak temp. °C	ΔH J/g
POCAMQ	130	195	78.3	7.53	1	106	140	119.00	160.00
Cu(POCAMQ) ₂	250	380	72.4	5.21	1	275	335	323.00	42.00
Ni(POCAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	190	280	71.3	4.86	1	175	265	236.50	106.50
Co(POCAMQ) ₂	250	280	60.0	4.53	1	230	255	248.10	109.00
Zn(POCAMQ) ₂	305	345	65.0	5.92	1	290	330	309.80	196.70
Mn(POCAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	215	290	68.0	6.03	1	230	250	241.36	42.18
Hg(POCAMQ) ₂	250	340	55.5	5.48	1	255	320	321.40	56.00
Cd(POCAMQ) ₂	285	355	60.7	4.19	1	295	330	321.35	62.00
UO ₂ (POCAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	250	350	70.0	6.21	1	220	330	315.00	59.00
PMCAMQ	120	190	85.7	7.18	1	105	180	118.00	106.50
Cu(PMCAMQ) ₂	275	350	72.5	6.72	1	270	330	322.76	42.90
Ni(MPCAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	210	290	76.2	5.12	1	175	260	233.90	142.00
Co(PMCAMQ) ₂	225	305	65.4	5.89	1	210	260	248.00	110.00
Zn(PMCAMQ) ₂	275	310	79.8	6.28	1	290	340	309.75	196.70
Mn(PMCAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	225	380	70.0	5.67	1	245	325	314.69	59.66
Hg(PMCAMQ) ₂	280	375	69.7	4.78	1	265	335	321.90	87.00
Cd(PMCAMQ) ₂	275	320	63.4	4.37	1	280	315	323.65	55.50
UO ₂ (PMCAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	190	295	68.0	7.08	1	160	265	236.50	109.60

T_S = Starting temperature; T_E = ending temperature.

which is due to crystallisation temperature of the chelates. The metal chelates do not undergo any observable physical or chemical change before their thermal decomposition. The loss of two water molecules is noticed by the presence of weak endothermic peak in Ni^{II}, Mn^{II} and UO₂^{II} traces.

Antimicrobial activities : The Mannich bases POCAMQ, PMCAMQ and their metal chelates were studied for their antimicrobial behaviour towards *B. subtilis*, *P. fluorescens*, *E. coli*, *S. marcescens*, *A. niger*, *T. longibra-chiatum*, *P. stipitis* and *R. minuta*. POCAMQ and PMCAMQ showed 65–70% growth of all the test organisms compared to the control. The metal chelates (Ni, Hg and Cd) showed antimicrobial effect on all the test organisms, which may be due to inhibitory nature of Cd, Ni and Hg metal ions. The metal chelates of Cu, Zn and UO₂ showed stimulation of growth as compared to Mannich bases. Remarkable inhibition of *P. fluorescens*, *S. marcescens*, *A. niger* and *T. longibra-chiatum* was noticed (55–65%) with the Mn and Co metal chelates of POCAMQ and PMCAMQ Mannich bases, while the Zn chelates showed moderate growth. Thus the results suggest that variation in structure on coordination

affects the growth of microorganisms and may results into either inhibitory effect, stimulatory effect or reduction in toxicity of metal ions towards some microorganisms.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The Mannich bases was synthesised by the known method. To ethanol (50 ml) were added benzaldehyde (0.02 mol, 2.12 g) and *o*-chloroaniline or *m*-chloroaniline (0.02 mol, 2.55 g) followed by 8-quinolinol (0.02 mol, 2.9 g) and the mixture was left at room temperature for 45 days. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol-acetone mixture².

Metal complexes : To the Mannich bases (POCAMQ or PMCAMQ, 0.01 mol, 3.6 g) dissolved in DMF (100 ml) was added an aqueous solution (50 ml) of Ni^{II} acetate monohydrate (0.005 mol, 0.974 g) whereby the brown colour product separated out. The mixture was refluxed for 1h and the resulting solid was washed with hot distilled water, DMF and dried in an oven (60°), yield 3.5–4.0 g. Metal complexes of other metal ions were prepared in a similar manner. All the complexes were found insoluble in

common organic solvents.

C, H and N analyses were carried out on a Carlo-Erba instrument. Metal analyses were carried out by standard procedure²¹. Magnetic study was carried out at room temperature by the Gouy method. Reflectance spectra were scanned on a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer using MgO as a reference material and infrared spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer. Thermal study was made on a Du-Pont 951 analyser. The differential scanning calorimetry was performed on a general V2-2A Du-Pont 9900 instrument. Electrical conductivity was measured in air using a Hewlett-Packard 4329-A high resistance meter.

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